

The Innovation of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan Province, for Ecotourism

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Abstract—The main purpose of this research was to study how to communicate the identity of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province for ecotourism. The qualitative data was collected through studying related materials, exploring the area, in-depth interviews with three groups of people: three directly responsible officers who were key informants of the district, twenty foreign tourists and five Thai tourist guides. A content analysis was used to analyze the qualitative data. The two main findings of the study were as follows:

1. The identity of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province. This establishment was near the Mouth of the Gulf of Thailand for normal people and tourists, consisting of rest accommodations. There are restaurants where food and drinks are served, rich mangrove forests, Bangpoo seaside resort and mangrove trees. Bangpoo seaside resort is characterized by muddy beaches where the greatest number of seagulls can be seen from March to May each year.
2. The communication of the identity of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province which the researcher could find and design to present in English materials can be summed up in 3 items: 1) The history of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province 2) The Learning center of Ecotourism: Seagulls and Mangrove forest 3) How to keep Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province for ecotourism.

Keywords—Foreigner tourists, signified, semiotics, ecotourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

TOURISM is an important industry because it creates income for developing countries. Thailand realizes the importance of continuously developing its tourism industry. The country supports and promotes many activities and projects with advertisements and publications geared toward people who are in this area. Also, Thai people are beginning to realize the importance of preserving their tourism resources and supporting ecotourism. The Ministry of Tourism and Sports said 22.3 foreigners visited Thailand in 2013, with the Chinese (2.7 million) just topping Malaysians (2.5 million), followed by Russians (1.3 million), Japanese (1.3 million), Koreans (1.1 million), British (870,164) and Germans (681,566) [9]. This increase in tourists has boosted many local careers and income as well as helping develop the transportation, basic construction and public utilities in the local communities where tourism is important. The local people are less likely to emigrate to other places with these improvements in their own area.

Tourism in Thailand was recently affected by the changing

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world economy and natural disasters. The Tourism Authority of Thailand has continuously encouraged Thais to understand their Thai identities and the value of their historical sites, culture and tradition.

The tourism resources have recently been moving toward sustainable tourism [2]. The ecotourism industry in Thailand has achieved this. At the present, there are many aspects to manage effectively including various signs to the important places. There are some problems to group of tourists which are not clear such as signs to tell ways, signs for educational information of tourism sources. The location signs are only in the Thai language which can make it difficult for foreign tourists to understand. The information shows that the Thai identity is extremely necessary and important as a tourism resource. The way that the identity of the tourism resources is communicated is very important to help tourists understand and learn these ideals [6]. These groups are important to Thai tourism resources at Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province. In this research, The Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province is identified by: the history of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, and the learning center of the ecotourism: Seagulls and Mangrove forest. These topics are useful for both the Thai people and foreign tourists. The important problems took place at Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province. The communication to foreigners in English is the least important [7]. These situations may reduce the number of foreign visitors.

For this research, the researcher chose the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province to be the research area. This area is very interesting to foreign tourists and helps them understand the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province. ICOMOS (The International Council on Monuments and Sites) tries to communicate new events in the communities and the past civilization at the same time [4]. This function was too plain for the both the Thai people and the foreigner's younger generations to learn. If the researcher had not explored the topic for this paper, it is possible the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province would not understand this important tourism resource. The researcher is an English teacher who is interested in finding the identities of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province and the Innovation of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1. To study the data and analyze the identities of the identity of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism.

- To communicate the Identity of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism develop the sustainable materials as a communication some ecotourism.

III. METHODOLOGY

The Innovation of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism. This research is qualitative research. The objectives of this research are The Innovation of English Materials to Communicate the Identity of the Bangpoo district, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism.

A. Population and Samples

There are three groups of samples that are outlined in the following items:

- The key informant group in the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province is five persons: the chief persons and officers in the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province.
- The foreigner group is made up of ten people per day who visited Thailand. The researcher interviewed the thirty people for the foreigner group by the following criterions:
 - The foreigner group who had come in the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, Thailand more than one time.
 - The foreigner group who specially visited the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, Thailand, and did not go to any other places.
 - In this case for the foreigner group, if a group included two persons traveling together only one person was chosen for the interview.

There are also the following conditions:

- The age of the tourists interviewed is more than twenty years old.
- There are six tourists from Europe, seven tourists from America, four tourists from Australia, seven tourists from Canada and six tourists from Asia

TABLE I
 GROUP OF KEY INFORMANTS IN THE MUEANG DISTRICT, SAMUT PRAKRAN PROVINCE

General data of group of key informant	Gender		Age				Level of Ed.	
	F	M	25	31	36	45	B	M
Key informant group in Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province	2	3	1	2	1	1	3	2
Total	2	3	1	2	1	1	3	2

TABLE II
 GROUP OF FOREIGNER TOURISTS WHO CAME TO THE BANGPOO DISTRICT, SAMUT PRAKRAN PROVINCE

Samples group	G.		Age				Times			
	F	M	20	31	41	51	61	1	2	
Europe	5	8	4	2	2	5	0	8	5	
Australia	4	0	2	1	0	0	1	3	1	
Canada	5	1	1	3	1	1	0	4	2	
Asia	4	3	2	1	2	1	1	6	1	
Total	18	12	9	7	5	7	2	21	9	

TABLE III
 GROUP OF TOURIST GUIDES

Samples	Gender		Age			Working experience			Total
	M	F	25	31	41	2	6	11	
Group of Tourist guides	2	3	3	1	1	2	2	1	5
Total	2	3	3	1	1	2	1	2	5

IV. DELIMITATION OF RESEARCH PROPOSAL

During this research, the researcher conducted the study at the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, Thailand, to study the data to analyze the identity and communication at the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism. This study was conducted from October 2012 to September 2013 by triangulation methodology such as observations, asking questions, taking notes on the data and checking documents.

V. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Literature Review was conducted on the theory of sustainable tourism, the theory of communication, the theory of Semiology and other research for the conceptual frameworks for the following items:

The identities of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province

- The History of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan.
- The Learning source of Ecotourism: Seagull and Mangrove forest.

VI. RESEARCH INSTRUMENTS

The researcher used the qualitative method for this research. The research instruments consisted of in-depth interviews, direct observation and content analysis of written materials with the details below:

The interview was used in the unstructured-interview with both the Thai language and English language. The questions were divided by sample groups into the following items: Interview for key informant group in the Banpoo, Samut Prakan province had two parts, each is listed below:

Part I General information of interviewers consisted of name, surname, gender, age, education, status, and position at the Bang poo, Samut Songkan province.

Part II The Interview Questions are listed below:

- The history of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan Province
- The Learning center of Ecotourism: Sea gulls and Mangrove forest

Interview for tourist guides had two parts, each is listed below:

Part I General information of interviewers consisted of name, surname, gender, age, education, status, position at the Banpoo, Samut Prakan province.

Part II The Interview Questions are listed below:

- How do you know the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province?
- What is the identity of the Bangpoo in Samut Prakan province according to your own idea? Please give examples.
- What do you want to communicate to others about the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province?

4. In what matters do foreign tourists recognize the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province?
5. How can you help preserving the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province for ecotourism?
6. What are your suggestions to promote tourism at this tourist attraction?
7. What are the problems that affect foreign tourists at the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province?
8. How do you keep the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province for ecotourism?
9. What are the big images of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province according to you?

A conclusion section is not required. Although a conclusion may review the main points of the paper, do not replicate the abstract as the conclusion. A conclusion might elaborate on the importance of the work or suggest applications and extensions.

VII. OBSERVATIONS

Observations were collected to provide a content analysis of written materials at the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province. They consisted of the contents analysis to communicate about the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, Seagulls and Mangrove forest and nearby environmental areas.

VIII. RECORDS THE CONVERSATION IN A GROUP

A. Workshop

The data was collected from field trips and separated by each categorical variables topic of research.

B. Taking Notes

The researcher took notes at each interview and used equipment such as a recorder, a camera, etc.

IX. DATA COLLECTION

A. Survey Study

The researcher collected the data by reviewing of literature and documents related to surveyed areas and collected the data from literature that were related to surveyed areas of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province.

B. Key Informants

The researcher had an appointment with the five key informants for in-depth interview at the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan

C. Group of Tourists

The researcher interviewed the tourists who visited the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province by interviewing thirty tourists from Europe, Australia, Canada and Asia.

D. Tourist Guides

The researcher asked the five tourist guides the following questions in their interviews.

X. ANALYZING THE DATA AND WRITING THE RESEARCH REPORT

The researcher collected the data from the interviews, studied the data and the documents and analyzed the content analysis. The researcher used the data of interviews from key informants, foreigner tourists and tourist guides. The researcher took photographs and recorded the documents. After that, the researcher gathered the conclusion from the answers and discussions in a research report following the conceptual framework and the theories outlined in this paper. The researcher described the report and related information in the content analysis.

XI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This report analyzed "The design of English materials to communicate the identity of Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province for sustainable tourism by the following two items:

1. The history of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province
2. The Learning center of ecotourism: Seagulls and Mangrove forest

The ecotourism has occurred because of the affections of the national resources [1]. It was a center of learning about natural resources, a pleasure to view the mangrove forest scenery, plants and animals including mangroves, cork trees and fireflies. They were found in Cembalos' research, 2011. And Bushel's research in Interpretation in National Parks: Some Critical Questions. The communication for the natural resources found that the communication should be geared toward ecotourism and stress the knowledge and the suggestions in the natural resources crossing the cultural divide: Western visitors and interpretation at Ayutthaya World Heritage Site, Thailand. The researcher found that the communication should show the highlight, preparing the manual for services and giving the information to the information center [10]. Moreover, it should create leaflets and a CD of the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province. The communication should show meaning and important things which were found in [8]. Reference [3] mentioned the communication showed the information and true facts. Offering every type of communication means giving the information and presenting it to natural sciences and history classes. It made the tourists feel better and better understand the content. It increased the tourists' morale to protect the natural environments for local persons, tourist guides and government officers who were responsible the natural resources [5]. The communication in the English language is very important for the Bangpoo, Samut Prakan province, for ecotourism. Studying the identities of the natural resources in the international language of English, made it easier for the foreign tourists to understand the identity of the natural resources in Thailand.

Fig. 1 Bangpoo Nature Educational Centre

Fig. 2 Seagulls at Suk Ta Bridge, Bangpoo

XII. SUGGESTION FOR THE NEXT RESEARCH

This research can be applied to the next research on other natural resources or historical sites, tradition and culture where searches for the identity of local culture are needed any sites that is interested in ecotourism in the future would be a good location to study.

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